

I-CLAIM

Improving the Living
and Labour Conditions
of Irregularised Migrant
Households in Europe

Irregularised migrants in the Delivery Sector (Berlin)

Sector report

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Executive Summary

The present report offers a synopsis of the principal findings of WP5 within the broader I-CLAIM Project, with a particular focus on the working conditions of migrants in the food delivery sector in Berlin. It provides a contextual analysis of the platform economy in the city, and an examination of the experiences of migrant workers as international students. For the international students, financial dependence on insecure employment in the platform economy combined with the high cost of living in the city results in significant precarity. Additionally, many migrants were only able to finance their migration trajectory through loans taken out in their home countries, which drives them into a spiral of debt. Despite ongoing efforts by the trade union for Food, Beverages, and Hospitality (*Gewerkschaft Nahrung-Genuss-Gaststätten*) to advance labour struggles in the sector of food delivery, the platform economy hinders worker mobilization through the lack of transparency regarding contracting parties and employers, as well as continuous pressure on employees. Overall, the immediate recruitment of mostly young early-career migrants from third countries upon their arrival reflects a strategic exploitation of individuals who are inexperienced and typically harbour strong aspirations to enter the labour market in Germany. The report also includes a description and reflection on the ethnographic methodology employed. In this vein, the community researchers who assisted access to the migrants helped secure the perspectives of four female riders.

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1. Introduction

This study explores the complexities of irregularity within the platform economy, focusing on how migrant workers navigate precarious employment conditions while being shaped by their migration trajectory, work circumstances, and residence permits. By examining the interplay between these factors, the research sheds light on the structural vulnerabilities that migrant workers – predominantly from the Global South – face in platform-based labour.

Thereby, this ethnography examines how migrant workers engage with and navigate the platform economy, with a focus on the complex relationship between their migration status, work conditions, and residence permits. It explores the role of student work contracts and student visas, which often serve as entry points into the labour market but also contribute to migrants' vulnerabilities. The study outlines how work in the platform economy affects not only migrants' financial situations but also their personal and family lives, as many workers are caught in a cycle of debt repayment that delays their ability to achieve social mobility or return to their home countries. Additionally, the research investigates the structural challenges migrant workers face, including the lack of job security, safety, and collective action opportunities in the platform economy, which ultimately shapes their long-term prospects and decisions.

The findings highlight that migrant workers in the platform economy operate in an online-only, highly individualized labour structure with limited opportunities for collective action or worker solidarity. Many enter the workforce through student visas and temporary contracts, yet they find themselves caught in a vicious cycle of financial insecurity, forcing them to extend their stays rather than achieving upward mobility. The lack of institutional protections exacerbates their precariousness, as they work in an informal, unregulated environment with little recourse to labour rights. Ultimately, the research underscores the contradictions of platform-based labour: while it offers flexibility and immediate income, it also entrenches insecurity, making long-term planning difficult for migrant workers and their families.

2. Context

Three main companies dominate the platform industry in Berlin:

- **Wolt** founded and based in Helsinki (FI) in 2014, expanded to Germany in 2020, profiting from the Covid-19 pandemic and the resulting lockdowns. As of November 2024, Wolt operates in 59 locations within Germany. Wolt operates with several sub-companies (so-called fleet managers) who provide the workforce.
- **Lieferando**, since 2015 part of the takeaway company in the Netherlands, was originally founded in Berlin in 2009 and held a monopoly in the platform economy on the German market for a long time. Lieferando is the only company in the food delivery sector that hires their own labour force and has organized work councils (*Betriebsräte*), self-organized assemblies of employees who ensure working rights, in multiple cities.
- **Uber Eats** entered the German market in 2021 and is represented in over 100 cities within Germany. The company's business model exclusively relies on sub-companies who hire workers.

Among riders, and especially those hired by third parties, it is common to switch between companies or work for multiple ones. When probation periods end or contracts are terminated, riders quickly seek new free rider positions at Dominos, Foodpanda or Flink. Since the establishment of the platform economy to the German

market, trade unions have been lamenting working conditions and precarious circumstances. To a point in which trade union workers talk about “criminal underlying structures of businesses” through sub-companies and intermediaries who hire migrants upon arrival on illegal basis. Protests and actions have been increasing through the collaboration of trade unions and platform workers, especially riders. However, union organization and representation remain difficult undertakings due to the fast-paced nature of this sector: constant workforce turnover, no physical workplace, and social fragmentation within the company.

One grassroots movement that gained public attention and made an impact was the platform workers’ online campaign ‘*Liefern am Limit*’ (Delivering at the Limit) which started in 2017/18. The movement started collaborating closely with the German trade union for Food, Beverages, and Hospitality (NGG). Thanks to their consultations, work councils within Lieferando were formed in different cities and started advocating for collective labour agreements. In 2020, the trade union assumed leadership of the movement. Active on various social media platforms, ‘*Liefern am Limit*’ united platform workers nationwide and across companies under one voice. What had initially started as an activist movement turned into a trade union campaign over the years. The current demands include the establishment of a collective agreement with an hourly wage of at least 15 euros, the payment of a 13th-month salary, appropriate surcharges for holiday shifts, six weeks of vacation, and full payment for the last work-related journey home. Nevertheless, Lieferando tried throughout to diminish the movement’s efforts by terminating contracts during probation periods or cancelling shifts, thereby threatening workers. Similarly, governmental containment measures during the Covid-19 pandemic prevented plans for public demonstrations and gatherings. In her analysis of the movement, Schreyer (2024) concluded that the movement tends to represent privileged riders who are not existentially dependent on their job. She added, even though the movement tried to address migrant workers through English speaking content and translations, it seems language still represents a barrier.

In Berlin, delivery riders are predominantly young men between 20 and 35 years from the Global South, particularly from India, Pakistan, and Bangladesh. They typically migrate to Germany on student visas to pursue higher education. Upon arrival and leveraging pre-existing social connections with family members or co-nationals, these young men secure housing in shared accommodations or student housing facilities. Similarly, they are often recommended for delivery rider positions by acquaintances or co-national intermediaries, allowing them to bypass formal application processes or job interviews. As a result, many are hired through referrals. Communication and Onboarding is exclusively happening online.

Most of them begin working under student contracts that permit up to 20 working hours per week. Given that many migrants have taken out loans in their home countries to finance their studies and stay, working to repay these debts – along with the potential to send money home – becomes a primary motivation. This motivation is often enhanced when migrants realize living costs in Germany are higher than what they expected or had been informed about. As students who are enrolled at German Universities, health care costs have to be covered by migrants themselves, whilst transportation costs are included in their student fees. Few of the young migrants speak fluent German; most of them have a language proficiency of European Standard Level A1-A2. For many of them acquiring the German language is of little interest, because study programs are in English and plans for backward migration to home countries is generally planned from the very beginning. However, due to the workload and the physical demands of the job, migrants fall behind in their studies. This creates a vicious cycle in which migrants work to pay off debts and cover costs, while their stay in Germany keeps prolonging. Hence, it is often the case that some migrants, despite initially planning to return to their home countries, decide to stay in Germany and convert their student contracts as delivery

riders into full-time contracts once their studies are completed, in order to increase their earnings. Those who plan to stay in Germany also pursue full-time delivery rider positions as a means of securing a work visa.

In terms of networks and infrastructures, social media (Facebook, WhatsApp, Telegram) plays an important role in how platform workers communicate. In addition, common gathering spots in the city that are strategically located between restaurants are places in which migrant workers communicate with each other. Yet, due to short breaks and waiting time in-between orders, there is few possibilities for exchange. Some migrants report of restaurants that support them, by allowing them to spend their breaks or waiting time inside the restaurant, to use toilette facilities or by offering hot beverage and food. As there are organized Lieferando work councils in most of the cities, Lieferando riders are most often better connected between each other and receive more collegial support. In contrast, Wolt and Uber Eats riders operate in an online-only, highly individualized labour structure that impedes any legal formation of work councils and trade union work. In many cases, it is questionable if the work contract is directly with Wolt or if it runs with a sub-company.

Since these companies predominantly employ migrants who have only recently arrived in Germany, these workers are often poorly informed or entirely unaware of the labour rights applicable in the country. As a result, many mistakenly assume that vacation or sick days are not compensated under student contracts or are recorded as negative hours. Unlike in the gig economy, riders receive an hourly wage, including payment for idle time. Additionally, Lieferando offers a bonus upon reaching a specified number of deliveries.

3. Methodology

The data was collected over a six-month period, from October 2024 to March 2025. The ethnographic research was conducted in the city of Berlin. Half of the interviews with migrant workers took place in person within the city, most often during their working hours. The other half of the interviews was conducted online via Zoom and thus, off working hours. The respective circumstances influenced the nature and duration of the interviews. When interviews were conducted during working hours in the street the length of the interviews depended on their current workload. However, this approach also enabled the formulation of subsequent inquiries concerning clothing, equipment, bicycles, the functionality of the app, the primary point of contact in case of issues, and the manner in which migrant workers spent their breaks. All interviews were conducted in English, which all participants spoke fluently.

An Indian community researcher facilitated contact with participants and provided assistance when communication in English proved challenging. The role of gender in establishing contact was found to be significant, with the male community researcher noted for his particular usefulness in this regard. Some migrants stated at the end of the interview that they would not have agreed to participate or would not have responded if approached by a female researcher. This is due to social patriarchist structures in the home states of India and differed depending on the cultural and religious background of the interlocutor. The majority of participants opted to remain anonymous, with some choosing not to disclose their names, which made it challenging to secure follow-up interviews. The majority of interviewees consented to having their interviews recorded. As a form of remuneration for their participation, the migrant workers received a €25 voucher for a local supermarket.

However, after a limited number of interviews, the migrants' statements began to repeat themselves, indicating that a certain level of saturation with regard to the questionnaire had already been achieved. In order to expand the dataset new hubs were sought, i.e. new locations where migrant workers spend short waiting times or breaks, different company hubs. In addition, an attempt was made to introduce a variation by targeting riders with a visible other company (such as Lieferando). However, it was found that visible branding was not always an accurate reflection of the company with which the migrant worker was associated. Through previous research contacts and volunteer work in the field of migration/integration, the researcher was able to reach a new group of migrants and arrange interviews with them outside of working hours. These circumstances created a safer and more confidential atmosphere than in the other interviews, which in turn made it possible to ask questions about contract types, employers, and employment issues. Through this contact four female migrant riders were reached, adding a female perspective.

The community researcher was actively involved and participated during the interviews done in the streets, asking follow-up questions, providing clarification in Hindi, and making links to situations in their home countries. The community researcher had personally experienced the growth of the platform economy in India and was likewise familiar with research methods. He was in a position to offer insights into the similarities and differences between the economies in Germany and India. Furthermore, he functioned as an expert on common social motivations and cultural habits known from India, and his insight perspective helped him to read the migrants in terms of education, religion, region and social capital. The online interviews were conducted without the community researcher. In order to stay in contact with the migrants as much as possible and secure follow-up interviews, LinkedIn proved to be a useful platform, as migrants were willing to connect there, viewing the business contact as beneficial. In contrast, exchanging phone numbers was met with little interest. However, only two migrants were willing to meet again.

The analysis was conducted after transcription and with coding methods that look at repetitive statements and outstanding findings.

4. Main Findings from Ethnography

The main findings of this research highlight the precarious position of migrant workers within the platform economy, shedding light on how their migration status as international students and working conditions intertwine.

4.1. Migration Journey

Many migrants initially enter the platform economy through student work contracts, viewing these jobs as a temporary solution to support their studies or remain in Germany legally after graduation. On the question how long migrants plan to stay working as riders common answers are: "I don't know, now it is okay. After two years, one year, one month, I don't know, I change job. But I will change job". On questions if migrants seek for other social networks and jobs answers often point to lacks of opportunity and language barrier: "when I arrived I thought I will engage with people, but what I told you the language barrier, in 5-6 years I will go completely back to India, I am getting knowledge here and start my own business in my state". However, as their stay extends, they often become trapped in a cycle where their initial plans for return migration become increasingly difficult to realize.

Migrants typically migrate with the goal of completing their studies often at private universities, gaining international work experience and returning home after graduation, but financial debts and high living expenses combined with the precariousness of their employment status, delays their ability to achieve social mobility or save enough to return. As two riders from Pakistan describe, “expenses are higher [than expected]: rent, health insurance and university fees” and “Berlin very expensive, hard to find a job, sometimes no job”. If riders receive bonuses for the kilometres they travel, it creates work pressure that distracts them from their primary goals, such as successfully completing their studies (“I wish I had an office working student job; on the bike, I think, *how can I get more orders?* If I worked in an office, I could focus on my goals”).

In addition, for some migrants the fact that they are overqualified for the job becomes likewise a psychological burden of failure and depreciation, as one man from Delhi pointed out, “actually it is a very difficult job for us, because after doing masters, I am doing this delivery job just because I have to cover up my expenses”. Regular expenses that have to be covered include rent, health insurance, phone contracts, occasionally university fees and groceries. For most migrants rent is the highest expense and often finding an apartment in Berlin is such a burden that most migrants share apartments and even rooms with co-nationals or friends. Often, the process of searching for housing constitutes such a significant stressor that many migrants feel initially compelled to reside in sublet accommodations. This situation results in a continuous strain due to the ongoing search for permanent housing. In some instances, migrants have reported relocating up to six times per year within Berlin. For those individuals who have secured rooms in student dormitories, the situation tends to become more relaxed.

4.2. Gender and Household

In general, all interlocutors were young individuals from Pakistan and India who aimed to advance their careers through work experience and education abroad. Most of them take out a loan to afford the travel and local expenses. Female interviewees reported receiving financial support from their families back home. Only in rarer cases did male interlocutors report the same. All migrants perceived it as very uncomfortable to rely on this support, especially since the image of Europe in their home countries is often highly idealized, making it hard for relatives to understand how difficult it is to earn money there. Due to the rising expenses – often partially borne by the family – the pressure intensifies for the stay abroad to yield tangible returns upon the individual’s homeward migration, both economically and in terms of social mobility. Almost all migrant riders plan to stay in Germany after completing their studies to gain international work experience. They mostly plan to find a job in their field and enhance their professional skills and knowledge in Germany before returning to their home countries. Backward migration is perceived as failure when high debts still persist or when no noticeable work experience enriches the personal CV. Through international education and professional experience in Germany, individuals seek to enhance their qualifications, which are highly valued in their home country. This, in turn, fosters their aspiration for upward social mobility for them and their families upon their return.

4.3. Recruitment and Onboarding Process

In the beginning, the flexible nature of delivery economy jobs is appealing to many migrants, as it allows them to balance work with their studies. The ease of entry into the workforce as no qualifications are needed, coupled with flexible hours, makes the job seem like an ideal option. Most often riders are hired through acquaintances who already work as riders or through co-national or other intermediaries, so-called third parties, from which it might be assumed that they work for sub-companies. Third party hiring is very

common and in most of the cases, these third-party riders are 'leased' to Lieferando or Wolt during high seasons. After the seasons, contracts are usually terminated without any pre-notice. As one rider described:

"I just received an email on 30th of April that was saying we are no longer hiring you, because our contract with Lieferando has ended. So, I was shocked. I was about to work in Lieferando for a year and I am getting an email that you are not working from next day. So that was very shocking really for me, because as an international student, if you lose your job then, because we all survive on these earnings only, like rent, fees and all, and when you don't have a job the situation is really stressful for me, yeah."

Many of the migrants described the main necessitate for the delivery job as a real means of survival. Once hired onboarding processes differ depending on the company. Lieferando riders and third-party riders at Lieferando receive an online video training that introduces general traffic rules as well as safety guidelines. Riders at Flink, Wolt, Uber Eats or Domino sometimes are assigned a person who accompanies them during the first few hours of their shift, showing them the work procedures and rules to be followed.

4.4. Work Processes and Labor Conditions

The work process consists of logging in the app, by which the shift officially starts, and through which working hours are counted. Once logged in riders receive order numbers with instruction for pick-up and delivery routes. There is no possibility for rejecting orders in case riders fear routes are too long and bike batteries are low. The app usually has a function of customer service or support chat which is used to communicate with shift managers concerning e.g. accidents, need for a break, battery recharge, bike issues or other inconveniences like missing surnames or address information for delivery.

Many migrant riders complain about restaurants letting them wait for long which delays their delivery, but above all makes them lose time to get more orders which generate tip (cash or online). All riders heavily rely on tip by customers even though they receive an hourly wage. Moreover, migrants are promised to work 20 hours a week, yet they often were assigned only up to 12-15 hours which caused frustration. Most of the companies claim to provide migrants with bags, jackets, rain trousers, helmets and gloves. However, migrants often reported the handed-out equipment was of low quality, used hence dirty, incomplete or not provided at all. Moreover, while companies supply basic tools, these often fail to meet the workers' needs, such as adequate protection against cold weather or bags, which are not adjustable to the bike but have to be carried on the back (generally preferred by the companies). As a result, many migrant workers take it upon themselves to buy cloths, lease or rent better quality bicycles, which are insured but come at a personal cost averaging between €100 and €170 per month. This additional financial burden further strains their already limited income. In almost all interviews, migrant workers reported the use of their personal mobile phones. Only Lieferando pays a monthly compensation for the costs of mobile data used during shifts.

The fact that working hours are counted through online functions often dismisses how much time migrants put into arriving early at a hub (in case of Flink and Lieferando) to pick a good bike when there is no private one. In Dominos migrant riders reported, they were logged in by managers who would log them out when there were no orders leading to a not paid waiting time. Accidents are "bound to happen" – all migrants reported slipping with the bike, falling in front of the tram or other accidents. All riders interviewed in the street were not wearing helmets.

As there is no centralized official hub – apart from facilities available to Lieferando riders – riders working for Wolt and Uber lack designated spaces to take their breaks. This absence is particularly critical during the winter months, when there are limited opportunities to seek indoor shelter and breaks must be spent outdoors under harsh conditions. Furthermore, there is no provision of toilet facilities or sheltered areas for eating during breaks. In many cases, migrant workers rely on the goodwill of restaurant owners to access basic amenities, highlighting a significant gap in infrastructural support.

4.5. Working rights and Communication

Migrants are often recruited after arrival and in most cases, migrants are highly unaware of working rights in Germany. Common issues are: migrant workers assume it is normal they are not paid when they are on sick leave or holiday, although minimum wage must be paid out, some migrant workers especially when hired by third parties are paid by order instead of hourly. A lot of migrants are afraid to have their contracts terminated during the probation period. Hence, many of them do ride faster and do not report accidents or take sick leave or holidays when needed. Another factor contributing to their vulnerability is the absence of a physical space where migrant workers can interact with company managers or colleagues, as most processes are conducted exclusively online. This lack of a physical workspace not only makes it difficult for workers to forge connections or build networks but also reinforces the highly individualized nature of the economy, leaving workers isolated and without collective support. Additionally, managers remain in an invisible and untouchable sphere, further distancing themselves from the workers they oversee. One rider replied on the question of how internal communication with superiors and managers is accomplished, “[communication is happening] only with manager, he is from Turkish or Arabic country. We have a mediator to talk in English”. The fact that communication is assisted by a mediator who speaks English shows the obstacles and speaks to the lack of interest in properly supporting employees and being accessible to them. One must assume that the mediator is appointed and paid by the employer, which raises the question of how the employees can approach the manager without incurring additional effort. At the end of the fieldwork, migrants reported that communication was exclusively happening through the app and via chat, which raised the question of language models generated answers.

4.6. Female Voices

Four female riders were interviewed to capture the female voice. Notably, female riders often go through a more formal application process, applying online. Three of the female riders worked at Lieferando, and one female rider worked at Flink. An important finding is that female migrant riders reported of sexual assaults from customer side. Due to the fact that riders are instructed to deliver to the door and sometimes in remote areas by night, female riders face situation of risk of sexual assault and violence.

“there were people that were not nice to me. The people I am delivering to, they were, you know, they were not nice. Especially if I can...one time, I had to go to the customer who was so drunk, so he was not being nice to me. Especially like, kind of taking advantage of me. So yeah.”

The female rider did not report this case to the manager due to discomfort. However, she kept explaining these cases were common among female riders, as customers might be drunk or having a party and tend to discriminative, racist, sexist or violent behaviour. Female riders also tended to report more frequently (than male riders) about physical suffering caused by the job, e.g. back pain, sickness. In general female riders seemed more surprised by disparaging attitudes towards them. One rider reported, “in rainy season I fell in

the road, in front of the tram, but nobody helped me. I was really painful. I informed them, but there was no help. Actually, in the moment I had not so much pain. Nobody helped because I am an immigrant, or I don't know. (...) They just looked at me". Female riders generally reported receiving support from family members abroad. In accordance to the conversations held with female riders and the community researchers it can be assumed they are from higher income families.

4.7. Racial Dimension

Only a few migrants reported experiencing discrimination or racism from customers, employers, or restaurant owners. Isolated incidents included being treated as second-class – such as being ignored, made to wait, or spoken to in a condescending manner. All migrants reported experiencing discriminatory behaviour directed at them in public spaces. It remains unclear whether this behaviour is rooted in racism or stems from general frustration related to the perceived overabundance of delivery riders in urban traffic. When asked why he thought so many Indians work in the delivery sector, one interlocutor responded, "Well, first the Western people are hired, then the Asians, then the Latin Americans, and finally the Indians and Africans". Many of the migrants – who often speak flawless English and already have work experience or academic degrees – send out applications relentlessly. This points to the existence of racial hierarchy in hiring processes of the overall job market in Germany.

5. Concluding Remarks

The platform economy offers migrants an easy financial income and great flexibility but also exposes workers to significant risks. The lack of job security, the absence of safety training and structures, and the possibility of termination or receiving an official warning with little recourse leave workers in a precarious situation. These conditions are exacerbated by the online-only, individualized nature of platform work, where workers have limited opportunities for collective action or solidarity. Moreover, the use of student work contracts and visas, while offering an entry point into the labour market, also contributes to migrants' vulnerability. Often unaware of the full scope of their rights or the working conditions, many workers become more easily exploitable, unable to challenge the system effectively. The lack of institutional protections in an unregulated, informal environment adds to their sense of precariousness, further deepening their financial insecurity. The underlying structure of platform economy through sub-companies and third-party contracts opens a network in which irregular work forms are used at the disadvantage of migrant workers, especially when it comes to accidents, and in which trade union efforts to challenge these circumstances remain unsuccessful.

Despite their efforts to apply for other jobs, many migrant workers face barriers to securing more stable employment. As a result, they remain stuck in a vicious cycle of working long hours, accumulating debts, and becoming increasingly bound to the platform economy, which impedes their educational and personal aspirations. The job, initially seen as a temporary solution, becomes their primary means of survival, prolonging their stay in Germany and delaying their plans for upward mobility and eventual return to their home countries. In conclusion, the platform economy offers flexibility and immediate income, but it also entrenches a system of insecurity, where migrant workers are caught in a continuous struggle for stability. The lack of social protections and job security, coupled with the individualized nature of the work, makes long-term planning and progression difficult for migrants, highlighting the contradictions inherent in platform-based labour.

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Appendix 1

Topic List for Interviews with Irregular migrant workers

“Basic” topics for short interviews are in bold. For the longer interviews you can go more in detail into the life history, experiences in other countries, in other sectors.

You can address the topics in the order you find most suitable. Ask examples of their experience.

Status	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Migration trajectory: motivation to migrate (<i>incl. family perspective</i>), countries before arriving here, role of family/brokers in migration process 2. Immigration status changes and experiences with administrative procedures 3. Legal enforcement: fears of and experiences with migration officers/police/labour inspections (how to deal with it in everyday life?) 4. If they have a family HERE: immigration status of family members, impact of irregularity on their conditions. 5. If they have a family AWAY (How often can you meet? Could you reunite?) 6. Prospects for mobility in the future? (moving to another city/country)
<hr/>	
Sectors	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 7. Current/last job: employer, duration, recruitment (networks, social media, brokers), multi-employment 8. Working conditions: working tasks, work hours, salary, relationship with employer and employers’ family, relationships with colleagues, discrimination at work, health and safety 9. Jobs in an irregularized situation (character of irregularity, incl. undeclared work/partial contracts) 10. Impact of immigration status on working conditions & experience now & in the past (incl. experiences with labour inspections; also impact of Covid, Temporary Protection Directive) 11. Future plans for work (moving to another job/sector) <p><i>CHECK WHETHER OTHER FAMILY MEMBERS ARE WORKING IN THE SAME SECTOR AND THEIR CONDITIONS</i></p>

Livelihood

12. Housing conditions: quality of housing, costs, location, relationship with other inhabitants, relationship with landlord or employer who arranges housing

13. Experience with healthcare (including reproductive health)

14. Experience with welfare (foodbanks, childcare, social benefits, family allowances)

15. Experience with education and schooling (if applicable)

16. Experience with access to public space and transportation

17. Finances: bank account, possibility to save money, remittances

APPLY ALL THESE QUESTIONS TO FAMILY MEMBERS, IF THEY ARE WITH THEM (include race/discrimination & the impact of Covid)

Mobilisation

17. Access to different social support (personal networks, NGOs, faith organizations)

18. Experience in asking (legal) support for work related matters (e.g. lack or bad payments): support from church, friends, labour union, social media)

18. Experience in organizing with colleagues or activists to improve working (and living) conditions. Future plans in this respect.

CHECK ROLE OF FAMILY MEMBERS IN THIS

At the end of the interview, check if you have information on:

Gender	Family status
Age	N. of children/elderly to care for
Years of migration in the given country	Level of education
Years of migration in other countries	Languages spoken
Country of birth	Current legal status
Citizenship(s)	Type of job

Appendix 2

Table I

Expert Interviews	Gender	Nationality	Institution/Role
1	W	German	NGO
2	W	German	NGO
3	M	Syrian	NGO
4	M	Syrian	NGO
5	M	German	trade union
6	M	Turkish-German	lawyer

Table II

Migrant Interviews	Gender	Nationality	Region	Legal status
1	m	Pakistan		Student visa
2	m	Bangladesh		Student visa
3	m	India	Gujrat	Student visa
4	m	India	Punjab	Student visa
5	m	India	Delhi	Student visa
6	m	Pakistan		Student visa
7	m	India	Punjab	Student visa
8	m	India		Student visa
9	m	India	Punjab	Student visa
10	m	India	Amritsar	Student visa
11	m	India		Student visa
12	m	India		Student visa
13	m	India		Student visa
14	m	India		Student visa
15	m	India (follow up 5)	Delhi	Job-seeker visa (after ending study program)
16	m	India		Student visa

17	w	India	Student visa
18	w	India	Student visa
19	w	India	Student visa
20	w	India	Student visa
21	m	India (follow-up 8)	Student visa
22	m	India	Student visa

I-CLAIM Consortium

Utrecht
University

UNIVERSITY OF
BIRMINGHAM

Ca' Foscari
University of Venice
Department of Philosophy
and Cultural Heritage

UNIVERSITY
OF WARSAW

HELSINGIN YLIOPISTO
HELSINGFORS UNIVERSITET
UNIVERSITY OF HELSINKI

Katholische
Hochschule Mainz
Catholic University
of Applied Sciences

THE JOINT COUNCIL
for THE WELFARE
OF IMMIGRANTS

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